

Supplementary materials: Magnetoelastic coupling at the field-induced transition in $\text{EuAl}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$

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I. HEAT CAPACITY

Figure 1 compares specific-heat measurements performed on the same single crystal as studied in Ref. [1]. The measurements were repeated at different times under nominally identical conditions. The data show the field dependence of the specific heat measured at various temperatures. While the overall behavior and transition fields are reproducible, the transitions appear noticeably broader in the upper panel and sharper in the lower panel.

This difference most likely originates from the data-analysis procedure inherent to the relaxation method using a two-tau model. Owing to the very low thermal conductivity of the sample, the thermal relaxation times are exceptionally long, and each data point results from a heat pulse followed by a fitting procedure. Under such conditions, differences in the convergence behavior of the fitting algorithm—such as abrupt versus gradual adjustments of the relaxation parameters—can affect the apparent sharpness of the transitions.

Figure 2 presents the temperature dependence of the specific heat of $\text{EuAl}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ measured at zero magnetic field using two independent calorimetric methods: the relaxation method with a two-tau model and the long-pulse method. The two data sets show no quantitative differences within the experimental resolution, demonstrating the consistency of the two measurement techniques.

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FIG. 1. Field dependence of the heat capacity of $\text{EuAl}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$. Two data sets correspond to an initial scan (a) and a repeated scan (b) performed on the same sample.

FIG. 2. Temperature dependence of the heat capacity of $\text{EuAl}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ at zero magnetic field, measured using two methods: the long-pulse method (red circles) and the relaxation method (black circles)

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- [1] G. Bastien, Q. Courtade, A. Eliáš, T. Haidamak, P. Proschek, M. Dušek, J. Priessnitz, P. Baláž, and R. H. Colman, Quasi-two-dimensional ferromagnetism in the triangular magnet $\text{EuAl}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$, *Physical Review B* **110**, 094436 (2024).